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- These materials are considered a work in progress. We are always reviewing and updating our processes and content in an evidence-based manner. New versions will be made available online.
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**Racial Equity and Inclusion Center
End of the Year Report**

2021

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Introduction

The Racial Equity and Inclusion (REI) Center is a pilot program aimed at identifying and addressing embedded **systemic racism** (green text denotes definition in glossary, Section 12.1), with a current focus on the Vollum Institute and the Neuroscience Graduate Program. We focus on both the personal and interpersonal aspects of racism via community transformation efforts, as well as the institutional and structural racism through innovative policies and procedures. Our center's work supports OHSU's 2020 pledge to its employees and to the broader community to become an anti-racist institution and is aligned with the first goal of the [OHSU 2025 Strategic Plan](#), which is to *"build a diverse, equitable environment where all can thrive and excel"*. OHSU recognizes that in order to realize the goal of building a diverse, equitable, and an anti-racist environment, the approach must be as multi-faceted as systemic racism itself. As Dr. Danny Jacobs [wrote](#):

"Transforming OHSU into a truly anti-racist and multi-cultural institution is a journey, and our goal is to continuously evolve our culture, policies and practices so that the environment at OHSU aligns with our ideals."

To achieve our anti-racism goals, our institution must:

- Adopt a **systems lens** for all equity work. For racial equity work, we must identify and address ways that we uphold systemic racism within ourselves, our relationships, within our institutional policies and procedures, and within our structure;
- Learn and apply **racial equity principles, values**, and frameworks to guide our anti-racism approaches;
- Provide the necessary racial equity educational foundation to our learners, staff, and faculty *and* apply our learnings in our everyday work;
- Provide our community with the necessary resources (e.g., personnel, financial, educational, and emotional support) to carry out transformative racial equity work and create an equitable environment.

These ideas map onto OHSU 2025 Strategic Plan Priority Objectives of a People first approach (Strategic plan, Section 1.1), Faculty/staff development (Strategic plan, Section 1.2), and Learner success (Strategic plan, Section 1.3).

At the REI Center, we use a systems lens, racial equity principles, values, and frameworks, for all of our work; from our center's structure to our everyday tasks. Two of our guiding values include transparency and accountability. To practice transparency, we will use annual reports to detail our work from the prior year. This is essential for our community to better understand our work and value, to hold us accountable, and to model the kind of transparency we hope to see from others. We hope this annual report helps communicate the value of REI Centers. We support the expansion of additional REI Centers outside of the Vollum Institute/Neuroscience Graduate Program that can provide local and tailored support to actualize our anti-racism goals across OHSU. Lastly, we are grateful for the community that we work alongside as their collective efforts help shape an environment aligned with our values.

-The REI Center Staff: Letisha Wyatt, PhD, Sarah Kisiwaa, PhD, and Antoinette Foster, PhD

1. REI Center Overview

1.1 The REI model concept

Many institutions across the country understand that to truly identify and address systemic racism and other intersecting systems of oppression, we benefit from a model where equity support services are embedded throughout the institution rather than centralized to one department for an entire university. This service distribution is one of the main premises behind the REI Center model. Similarly, institutions across the country have adapted this type of embedded structure that is tailor-fit to the unique equity needs of each **local unit** (e.g., [University of Michigan](#)). Currently, the REI Center concept is piloted with one local unit (the Vollum Institute/Neuroscience Graduate Program). This pilot is meant to provide an example to the broader OHSU community regarding: 1) identification of the essential components and workflow for an REI Center, 2) determination of staffing needs for an individual REI Center, 3) comparison to other racial equity strategies on campus. 2021 marks year 1 (YR-1) in this pilot program.

For a complete history of the genesis of the REI Center model at OHSU, please visit our previous publication [Revisioning OHSU's Approach to Racial Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion](#).

1.2 The REI Center structure

To move towards becoming an anti-racist institution, we all must learn how to identify and address embedded racism within ourselves and within our institution. In order to do this, it is essential to use a racial equity lens to craft and guide this work. This, in part, means addressing the many ways that systemic racism manifests: individual, interpersonal, institutional, and structural. With this framework in mind, we crafted the REI Center staffing positions specifically to address these manifestations. The two director positions within the REI Center use a systems and racial equity lens to understand and address system racism and other intersecting **systems of oppression**. The 2021 REI Center positions are described below:

Position title	Staffed by	Position description	FTE
Director of Innovative Policy	Dr. Letisha Wyatt	Focuses on institutional policies, procedures, and practices and the structural manifestation of systemic racism by comprehensively reviewing and revising current policies affecting students, faculty, postdocs, and staff within the Neuroscience Graduate Program.	0.5

		The Director of Innovative Policy has the responsibility to evaluate current processes and implement new and revised policies and procedures to address racial equity within the Institute.	
Director of Community Transformation	Dr. Antoinette Foster	Focuses on the personal and interpersonal manifestations of systemic racism. Addressing internalized and interpersonal racism requires education and community trust. Works alongside the local community to provide a pathway for anti-racism/anti-oppression education and training. Facilitates community participation which allows for collaborative and inclusive community building - a critical aspect for community transformation.	1.0
REI Center Postdoctoral Scholar	Dr. Sarah Kisiwaa	Focuses on supporting all of the REI Center functions. This type of scientifically trained racial equity postdoctoral position is unique within the scientific enterprise. Responsibilities include but are not limited to developing and delivering racial equity educational content, assisting in the development of equitable policy change, supporting PEER (Persons historically excluded from science due to race and ethnicity) students, postdocs, staff, and faculty, and providing support for building the necessary internal systems, operational plans, and best practices to achieve cultural shifts.	1.0

2. Major takeaways from pilot YR-1

- 1) **Our center has received overwhelmingly positive feedback from both students and faculty:** Quantitative and qualitative feedback show repeated themes related to the importance of working on a “local unit” level. Many individuals, programs, and leadership within departments want to engage in meaningful equity work that examines personal and interpersonal racism as well as racism within their department/programs, but need resources, education, guidance, and personnel support to do so. The REI Center is embedded within the Vollum Institute, which also uniquely houses the Neuroscience Graduate Program, which structurally supports advancing racial equity at a *local level*. Working on a local level allows us to:
 - a) Have a specific body responsible for advancing equity work within the local unit.
 - b) Build personal relationships and trust with students, faculty, and staff and focus on specific community needs (**See feedback in Section 5.1, 6.3-5, 8 and 9.2**).

- c) Respond to equity concerns or provide support faster and more thoroughly than **top-down approaches**. This also allows us to have a higher visibility and accessibility for PEER community members to work on solutions that matter to the local community and PEER community members specifically (**See feedback in Section 7.1**).
 - d) Co-create solutions with the local community (**See feedback in Section 6.5 and 9.1-2**), thereby empowering community members to become active change agents; and co-create/co-imagine **transformative futures**. These are all essential components for **Emergent Strategy**¹, **anti-racism**, and **anti-white supremacy culture principles**.
- 2) **Position FTE:** Each center requires the two director positions mentioned above to efficiently focus on different forms of embedded racism. Each position requires 1.0 FTE and each director needs at least one post-doctoral scholar in order to make significant contributions for a local unit of 150-200 employees. Although the REI Center currently has only one postdoctoral scholar, two postdoctoral scholars would provide a more appropriate level of support, which is needed to simultaneously advance both innovative policy and community transformation goals.
- 3) **REI Center staff must hold a base knowledge of racial equity core competencies and apply this knowledge to the local unit:** REI Center staff need an in-depth historical and present time understanding of systems of oppression and **liberating principles and practices** (Racial Equity Core Competencies, Section 12.2). Additionally, REI Center staff need to understand the ways in which systems of oppression manifest within their local unit. This is critical, as systemic oppression is embedded differently across units. For example, for an REI Center to be effective within the Vollum Institute and the Neuroscience Graduate Program, the REI Center staff need to understand the ways that inequities have and continue to be embedded across the scientific enterprise. Future REI Centers will need to be specific to the local unit. This type of specificity allows history to be uniquely tailored to the local unit, for instance, in understanding the ways systemic racism has been embedded into medicine versus biomedical research. This specificity contextualizes oppressive history, making the content and equity work personal and more meaningful to that community. Importantly, this strategy allows for the REI Center staff to specifically target unique areas of inequity within the local unit.
- 4) **Racial equity work must start with leadership engagement:** Leadership sets the tone for the local culture within a department/institute/program, and it is essential that:
- a) Leadership and REI Center staff co-develop their goals, vision, and values and publish a public statement to communicate these aspects to their local unit and to a broader community.
 - b) Leadership master core racial equity competencies in order to develop a racial equity lens and to apply these competencies to their work.

¹brown, adrienne maree. Emergent Strategy: Shaping Change, Changing Worlds. United Kingdom, AK Press.

3. Year in review

Figure 1: Visual depiction of REI Center efforts for YR-1.

The table below details all of the REI Center efforts for pilot YR-1.

Completed REI Center Initiatives	Initiative Milestones	REI Center Effort	Alignment with OHSU 2025 (Strategic Plan)
Co-create (with leadership) a Vollum Institute/Neuroscience Graduate Program racial equity statement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Write document - Published online 	<p><u>Lead:</u> Director of Community Transformation</p> <p><u>Support:</u> Edited with the Director of Innovative Policy and Postdoctoral Scholar</p>	<p>Goal 1: Build a diverse, equitable environment where all can thrive and excel.</p> <p>Priority Objective 1.1: People First</p>
Develop and Implement Leadership Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop leadership competencies, curriculum, and other educational materials - Facilitate educational sessions 	<p><u>Lead:</u> Director of Community Transformation</p> <p><u>Support:</u> Educational sessions facilitated with the Director of Innovative Policy and Postdoctoral Scholar</p>	<p>Goal 1: Build a diverse, equitable environment where all can thrive and excel.</p> <p>Priority Objective 1.2: Faculty/staff development</p>
New course-for-credit, "Navigating the Complexities of Graduate School"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create syllabus, course content, and acquired OHSU approval - Facilitate course (summer term) - Evaluate the course 	<p><u>Lead:</u> Director of Community Transformation</p> <p><u>Support:</u> Course syllabus, content, and facilitation with the Postdoctoral Scholar</p>	<p>Goal 1: Build a diverse, equitable environment where all can thrive and excel.</p> <p>Priority Objective 1.3: Learner success</p>
New course-for-credit, "Racial Equity in Research and Beyond"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create syllabus, course content, and acquired OHSU approval - Facilitate course (winter term) - Evaluate the course 	<p><u>Lead:</u> Director of Community Transformation</p> <p><u>Support:</u> Course syllabus, content, and facilitation with the Postdoctoral Scholar</p>	<p>Goal 1: Build a diverse, equitable environment where all can thrive and excel.</p> <p>Priority Objective 1.3: Learner success</p>
Enhance Recruitment of prospective PEER applicants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluate current advertising - Develop an advertising inventory with recommendations for new passive and active advertising strategies - Create the new process/identifying responsible personnel - Annual evaluation of advertising strategies 	<p><u>Lead:</u> Director of Innovative Policy</p> <p><u>Support:</u> Edits of advertising inventory by the Postdoctoral Scholar</p>	<p>Goal 1: Build a diverse, equitable environment where all can thrive and excel.</p> <p>Priority Objective 1.1: People First</p>
Neuroscience Graduate Program Admissions Process Improvement - Racial Equity Essay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify effective strategies for improving admissions process - Create application prompt and essay guidelines - Create essay evaluation materials - Develop and implement short- and long-term training and collaboration plan for admissions faculty - Annual evaluation of admissions program outcomes 	<p><u>Lead:</u> Director of Innovative Policy</p> <p><u>Support:</u> All milestones executed with the Director of Community Transformation and the Postdoctoral Scholar</p>	<p>Goal 1: Build a diverse, equitable environment where all can thrive and excel.</p> <p>Priority Objective 1.1: People First Priority Objective 1.3: Learner success</p>
Monitoring and Addressing Salary Adjustments for Vollum Institute Postdoctoral Scholars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consult with administrative officials and Director of Postdoc Affairs and work with Vollum Institute leadership on a process for pay remediation - Support Vollum Institute leadership in communications with postdocs and faculty - Establish mechanism for annual communication to postdocs and faculty, salary review and adjustments if required, and process maintenance 	<p><u>Lead:</u> Director of Innovative Policy</p> <p><u>Support:</u> All milestones executed with the Director of Community Transformation and the Postdoctoral Scholar</p>	<p>Goal 1: Build a diverse, equitable environment where all can thrive and excel.</p> <p>Priority Objective 1.1: People First</p>

4. Finances and budget

The REI Center is supported by the Research and Innovation Office overseen by the OHSU Chief Research Officer and Executive Vice President, Dr. Peter Barr-Gillespie. Our operating costs for YR-1 are as follows:

Category	Cost
Personnel (2.5 FTE) (Salary + Benefits)	~ \$350,000
Conference attendance	\$900
Total	\$350,900

Looking forward, we expect to increase our operating costs to include conference attendance, invited guest speakers, and community building, educational, or training events (especially once in-person events resume). At this time, the majority of the operating costs for the REI Center funds the personnel.

To appropriately advance both innovative policy and community transformation goals, our future budget should include funding to cover additional personnel (adding 0.5 FTE to the Director of Innovative Policy position plus 1.0 FTE for a second post-doctoral position).

Additionally, the REI Center received an Early-Stage Technology Development Award from OHSU's Technology Transfer in the amount of \$10,000. The REI Center proposed to use these funds to cover our website development and to support other ongoing REI Center activities.

5. Leadership Learn sessions

Meaningful engagement of anti-racism work requires a historical and social education related to race, colonization, and systems. Without understanding our past, we cannot understand our present. For a cultural shift to occur, leadership must engage with these concepts in depth as well, and especially prior to taking anti-racist action. This step is critical as leadership sets the tone for any environment and acts as an example for the community.

Although there may be several leaders within a given space, leadership within this context of this current pilot refers to the Director and co-Director of the Vollum Institute and the Director and Administrator of the Neuroscience Graduate Program. There are three core competencies: Learn, Grow, and Act (Section 12.2).

5.1 Leadership Learn Session Description

The Vollum Institute and Neuroscience Graduate Program leadership engaged in weekly “Learn” sessions with the REI Center staff. Specifically, the Director of Community Transformation used the REI Center Racial Equity Core Competencies to build weekly homework assignments meant to: 1) provide a historical and current-day understanding of systemic oppression from a race-centered lens; 2) create an opportunity for leadership to practice discussing race in small group settings; 3) facilitate co-creation of the anti-racism vision, values, and YR-1 objectives; 4) have leadership practice applying racial equity concepts to real-life policy and practices within the institute.

From these meetings, we co-developed the [Racial Equity Statement](#) for the Vollum Institute and Neuroscience Graduate Program. This statement aims to embody the characteristics of a meaningful racial equity statement, which outlines: 1) a description of the problem we aim to address using a systems and racial equity lens, 2) our overall anti-racism strategy, 3) our current objectives for YR-1. We encourage others to use this racial equity statement as a reference for creating more detailed and meaningful statements for their local unit.

Additionally, REI Center staff and Vollum Institute/Neuroscience Graduate Program leadership attended a five-day conference with the [National Conference for Race and Ethnicity in Higher Education](#) (NCORE). REI Center staff views NCORE attendance as an important supplement to the Leadership Learn sessions as this meeting helps contextualize the lessons or curriculum.

“The Vollum Institute leadership is committed to creating an inclusive environment where everyone feels valued, can thrive, and do their best work. Improving our environment from a cultural perspective is one of the key steps to achieving this goal, but first requires a good understanding of what our culture is, what biases are embedded in it, where we are succeeding, and where we need to grow and do better. Our work with the REI center has been invaluable for helping the leaders (Freeman and Monk) begin gaining a much deeper understanding of all of these issues. There are few topics/areas I have spent more focused time on over the last year, and I think the experience has made such a lasting mark on me. It has been illuminating, enjoyable, and painful all at the same time. The LEARN sessions have been in together have been the focal point for this work, and has inspired a lot of additional exploration on my own. We obviously don’t have all the answers yet, and need to continue to do work, but we feel very good about the direction we are moving in. Kudos to the REI team.”

(Marc Freeman; Faculty/ Director of the Vollum Institute)

6. Graduate Student Coursework

The REI Center created three separate courses for Fall 2021. The first course, *NEUS 618: Navigating the Complexities of Graduate School*, helped prepare students with the tools to navigate the socio-political aspects of scientific research. This course used an equity lens to learn about and discuss mentor/mentee relationships, nonviolent communication strategies, and ways to navigate potential conflict in graduate school.

Dr. Sarah KISSIWAA created the *NEUS 619: Effective Scientific Presentations*. Although this course did not focus specifically on racial equity, Dr. KISSIWAA applied the racial equity principles and values in the creation and delivery of this course which promoted an inclusive learning environment.

Additionally, an important YR-1 goal was to provide a pathway for graduate students to learn the REI Center Racial Equity Core Competencies (Section 12.2) and to engage in racial equity/transformational work that impacts their departments all while *receiving course credit* towards completion of their degree. Receiving credit is important, as most “diversity work” is advanced at universities through volunteerism - a practice we aim to reduce or eliminate. Towards this goal, both Dr. Foster and Dr. Kisiwaa created *NEUS-644: Racial Equity in Research and Beyond*. This course taught the REI Center Racial Equity Core Competencies and adapted them to the needs of students in research training environments.

All coursework led by the REI Center staff shared and followed the REI Center Code of Conduct (see Section 12.3), guiding values, and class structure.

Note: Please see the appendix for a detailed syllabus for each class (Section 12.3-12.5).

6.1 Course guiding values and philosophies

In addition to the values stated in the REI Center Code of Conduct, REI Center coursework aimed to practice vulnerability, accessibility, flexibility, centering the marginalized, and genuinely centering student needs. We practiced deep vulnerability by sharing our personal experiences within the context of each class. Sharing our personal stories aided in the creation of a space where students felt safer to share their personal stories, questions, and experiences about race as well. This, along with acknowledgement and discussions about power and privilege, facilitated the creation of a **brave space**. We actively sought out student’s opinions regarding the direction of the course and modified the course based on their feedback and needs. Examples of this include modifying the amount of homework, changing homework due dates, modifying course content, and by increasing accessibility of the content through manual transcription of videos or finding transcripts. Providing flexibility, accessibility, and valuing the importance of student needs helped cultivate a community of trust. This allowed for the added benefit of individual students coming to us to find support outside of the classroom. These practices are key elements for creating an inclusive environment.

People often wonder how to create racial equity and part of the answer is to center the needs of others, shedding our own relationship to power, and practicing behaviors aligned with anti-racism principles, anti-white supremacy principles, and concepts of emergent strategy. We are grateful for the opportunity the students provided for us to create community, share, learn, cry, and grow together.

6.2 Course structure and evaluation

All REI Center coursework was structured similarly and somewhat unconventionally compared to traditional coursework. Class time was 100% discussion-based rather than lecture-based. The reflection, growth, and honesty that happens in small group discussions led to deeper transformation. We found that much of the content that is required for any of our coursework already exists and is freely available online. Students were regularly given reading for homework, reflection questions ahead of class, and were asked to come prepared to discuss the content. We employed a concept called gDocing, which uses Google Docs to work collaboratively throughout class. Additionally, we structured each class around a philosophy called **Radical Participation**, which describes a system where every individual has something meaningful to contribute and participates accordingly. It places trust on the student to participate in ways they see fit, to contribute whatever is within their capacity at the moment, counts all contributions as important, and creates multiple pathways to engage (homework, class discussion, group work, etc.). In both of our courses, students predominately engaged using a variety of pathways. If we found that a student did not show engagement, we checked in with the student privately to identify and address any issues that may be preventing them from engaging and to offer support. By trusting and supporting the students, we strengthened our personal relationships, showing an overwhelmingly positive result for this strategy.

At the end of each course, we provided students with two formal opportunities to submit course evaluations. As with all OHSU coursework, students received the standard OHSU Course evaluation via BLUE. In addition, we created an additional opportunity for feedback via Qualtrics which allowed us to capture data on topics that are not addressed in the standard OHSU evaluation form. Examples include feedback on specific teaching methods, course formatting, the effectiveness of specific content and delivery modes, as well as specific questions about the REI Center. We contacted each student individually to gain their permission to use their anonymized data for this report. The data reflected in this report reflects feedback from these two separate evaluation forms.

6.3 NEUS 618: Navigating the Complexities of Graduate School

6.3.1 Course Evaluation (Quantitative)

Course Evaluation

The rating scale for the quantitative sections is described below:

- 6 - Strongly Agree
- 5 - Agree
- 4 - Slightly Agree
- 3 - Slightly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 1 - Strongly Disagree

Question	Average		SUBJ Avg. (Neuroscience)		DEPT-Avg. (Neuroscience- Portland Campus)	
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
The stated objectives were understandable.	6.00	0.00	5.81	0.40	5.81	0.40
The course as a whole was well organized.	5.57	0.53	5.58	0.56	5.58	0.56
The educational materials and resources enhanced my learning.	5.71	0.76	5.64	0.70	5.64	0.70
Evaluation of my performance was based on stated objectives.	5.71	0.49	5.55	0.89	5.55	0.89
The course content was appropriate to student knowledge at this point in the program.	5.86	0.38	5.77	0.50	5.77	0.50
The course content was linked to other courses in this program.	5.57	0.53	5.70	0.67	5.70	0.67
The course content was relevant to my graduate education.	6.00	0.00	5.85	0.36	5.85	0.36
The overall course demands were appropriate.	5.86	0.38	5.81	0.40	5.81	0.40
The course environment encouraged participation and involvement.	6.00	0.00	5.39	1.20	5.39	1.20
Overall, I rate this course highly.	5.86	0.38	5.76	0.44	5.76	0.44
Overall	5.81	0.43	5.69	-	5.69	-

Teaching Evaluation

Question	Average		SUBJ Avg. (Neuroscience)		DEPT-Avg. (Neuroscience- Portland Campus)	
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
The instructor was knowledgeable about the subject.	6.00	0.00	5.85	0.36	5.85	0.36
The instructor was well prepared.	6.00	0.00	5.89	0.32	5.89	0.32
The instructor's strategies stimulated my thinking and inquiry.	6.00	0.00	5.59	0.69	5.59	0.69
I received meaningful and timely feedback on my performance.	6.00	0.00	5.50	1.02	5.50	1.02
Overall, I rate this instructor highly.	6.00	0.00	5.81	0.40	5.81	0.40
The instructor was responsive to my concerns.	6.00	0.00	5.71	0.46	5.71	0.46
Overall	6.00	0.00	5.73	-	5.73	-

Data source: OHSU Course Standard evaluation platform (BLUE). 7 total respondents out of 10.

6.3.2 Course Evaluation (Qualitative)

Evaluation Question: What are the strengths of this course and or instructors?

"It really helped ease some of my fears of grad school and helped me feel more prepared for the parts of grad school that exist outside of the research. It was also a really good bonding experience with my cohort and helped me feel more similar to them rather than "they are the competition," because we shared many similar experiences and feelings. I liked that it was discussion-based and radical participation was required because it kept me engaged rather than listening to a lecture. Again, this helped foster a solid community. I think all the topics covered were useful and applicable to our training. I liked the shared google doc too!"

"Antoinette is very articulate and clearly puts a lot of thought behind her words, which makes them really impactful and memorable. Her candor about her own experiences inspired me to share more and be more honest. Sarah kept a really great energy throughout the course and was good at explaining the discussion sections and managing the class (eg breakout rooms). She also shared really openly about her experiences which gave a really helpful perspective and encouraged us all to share as well."

"Sarah and Antoinette were great instructors and they made it clear that they were advocates for the students. They did a great job preparing the course to set us up with a wide range of tools to tackle graduate school as first years. They covered difficulty topics to make sure we weren't taken by surprise by them later in our grad school experience. They were engaging, organized, and passionate. I'm grateful we were given the opportunity to take this course from them."

Evaluation Question: If the class helped prepare you for graduate school in any way, please describe how it helped your preparation:

"I came into the course feeling like grad students are inevitably going to be exploited by their PIs. This course helped me to feel supported by staff and faculty and equipped me with skills and tools to have a healthy and productive graduate training experience."

"I feel like this class had various useful conversations on topics/ideas that I didn't think I should think about before heading into grad school. Hearing the mentors and other students of the class was beneficial and I feel like I learned quite a bit from everyone."

"It helped me learn a lot more about grad school in general and things that go on outside of research and how to navigate many different relationships and where to seek help if needed. It helped me feel more confident in determining what I want to get out of grad school and how to achieve that."

"I feel better informed in the "soft" expectations and rules of grad school. For example, I did not know how much weight mentorship carried, and how to navigate those relationships. I would argue that the lessons of needs/values, mentorship, and culture are critical to a graduate students' success, and this course covered just that and gave us the tools and confidence to handle them."

6.3.3 Course Improvement Recommendations

- Shorter class periods broken up over the three weeks rather than 3.5-hour long classes
- More breaks integrated throughout the class time
- In-person classes rather than virtual

6.4 NEUS 619: Effective Scientific Presentations

6.4.1 Course Evaluation (Quantitative)

Course Evaluation

The rating scale for the quantitative sections is described below:

- 6 - Strongly Agree
- 5 - Agree
- 4 - Slightly Agree
- 3 - Slightly Disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 1 - Strongly Disagree

Question	Average		SUBJ Avg. (Neuroscience)		DEPT-Avg. (Neuroscience-Portland Campus)	
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
The stated objectives were understandable.	6.00	0.00	5.81	0.40	5.81	0.40
The course as a whole was well organized.	5.60	0.55	5.58	0.56	5.58	0.56
The educational materials and resources enhanced my learning.	6.00	0.00	5.64	0.70	5.64	0.70
Evaluation of my performance was based on stated objectives.	6.00	0.00	5.55	0.89	5.55	0.89
The course content was appropriate to student knowledge at this point in the program.	5.80	0.45	5.77	0.50	5.77	0.50
The course content was linked to other courses in this program.	6.00	0.00	5.70	0.67	5.70	0.67
The course content was relevant to my graduate education.	6.00	0.00	5.85	0.36	5.85	0.36
The overall course demands were appropriate.	6.00	0.00	5.81	0.40	5.81	0.40
The course environment encouraged participation and involvement.	6.00	0.00	5.39	1.20	5.39	1.20
Overall, I rate this course highly.	6.00	0.00	5.76	0.44	5.76	0.44
Overall	5.94	0.24	5.69	-	5.69	-

Teaching Evaluation

Question	Average		SUBJ Avg. (Neuroscience)		DEPT-Avg. (Neuroscience-Portland Campus)	
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
The instructor was knowledgeable about the subject.	6.00	0.00	5.85	0.36	5.85	0.36
The instructor was well prepared.	6.00	0.00	5.89	0.32	5.89	0.32
The instructor's strategies stimulated my thinking and inquiry.	5.67	0.58	5.59	0.69	5.59	0.69
I received meaningful and timely feedback on my performance.	6.00	0.00	5.50	1.02	5.50	1.02
Overall, I rate this instructor highly.	6.00	0.00	5.81	0.40	5.81	0.40
The instructor was responsive to my concerns.	6.00	0.00	5.71	0.46	5.71	0.46
Overall	5.94	0.24	5.73	-	5.73	-

Data source: OHSU Course Standard evaluation platform (BLUE). 5 total respondents out of 10.

6.4.1 Course Evaluation (Qualitative)

Evaluation Question: What are the strengths of the course and or instructors?

"The instructors did a great job engaging students in the material and providing non–science examples. They also did an AMAZING job fostering a low–stress and open environment for students to practice their presentation skills. The overall material presented, particularly in discussing the structure and formatting of PowerPoints and posters, was massively helpful!"

"Going through examples of presentations to learn what is effective and what can be improved. Having an on–going google doc to make this course more discussion–based than sitting and listening to a lecture. The pace was good and easy to follow. Each class touched on a different topic when it comes to scientific presentations and I feel like I have a lot of knowledge and understanding to what goes into the various forms of presentations. It was also nice to give a final presentation at the end and I am looking forward to reading my feedback."

"The material was engaging and interesting. The instructors did a great job expressing genuinely helpful constructive criticism during final practice presentations."

6.4.2 Course Improvement Recommendations

- Longer course duration to allow for more time to make a presentation and practice
- A way to measure progress or improvement, for example with a presentation at the start of the course

REI Center

6.5 NEUS 644- Racial Equity in Research and Beyond

6.5.1 Course demographics

6.5.2 Course Evaluation (Quantitative)

Course Evaluation

The rating scale for the quantitative sections is described below:

6 - Strongly Agree

5 - Agree

4 - Slightly Agree

3 - Slightly Disagree

2 - Disagree

1 - Strongly Disagree

Question	Average		SUBJ Avg. (Neuroscience)		DEPT-Avg. (Neuroscience-Portland Campus)	
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
The stated objectives were understandable.	5.82	0.40	5.69	0.56	5.69	0.56
The course as a whole was well organized.	5.91	0.30	5.44	0.84	5.44	0.84
The educational materials and resources enhanced my learning.	6.00	0.00	5.49	0.83	5.49	0.83
Evaluation of my performance was based on stated objectives.	5.90	0.32	5.52	0.70	5.52	0.70
The course content was appropriate to student knowledge at this point in the program.	6.00	0.00	5.44	0.87	5.44	0.87
The course content was linked to other courses in this program.	4.40	1.82	5.34	0.91	5.34	0.91
The course content was relevant to my graduate education.	5.91	0.30	5.53	0.79	5.53	0.79
The overall course demands were appropriate.	6.00	0.00	5.62	0.61	5.62	0.61
The course environment encouraged participation and involvement.	6.00	0.00	5.52	0.73	5.52	0.73
Overall, I rate this course highly.	6.00	0.00	5.62	0.58	5.62	0.58
Overall	5.79	0.54	5.52	-	5.52	-

Teaching Evaluation

Question	Average		SUBJ Avg. (Neuroscience)		DEPT-Avg. (Neuroscience-Portland Campus)	
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
The instructor was knowledgeable about the subject.	6.00	0.00	5.83	0.38	5.83	0.38
The instructor was well prepared.	6.00	0.00	5.78	0.45	5.78	0.45
The instructor's strategies stimulated my thinking and inquiry.	6.00	0.00	5.78	0.45	5.78	0.45
I received meaningful and timely feedback on my performance.	6.00	0.00	5.75	0.57	5.75	0.57
Overall, I rate this instructor highly.	6.00	0.00	5.82	0.39	5.82	0.39
The instructor was responsive to my concerns.	6.00	0.00	5.75	0.57	5.75	0.57
Overall	6.00	0.00	5.78	-	5.78	-

Data source: OHSU Course Standard evaluation platform (BLUE). 11 total respondents out of 19.

Evaluation Question: Compared to the start of the term, how confident do you feel about contributing to a conversation on these topics in a safe place (whatever you consider to be a safe place)?

Figure 3: Student self-assessment on learning and confidence in understanding and discussing class topics. 15/20 Respondents

6.5.3 Course Evaluation (Qualitative)

Evaluation Question: What are the strengths of the course and or instructors?

"I so appreciated the instructors listening and actively seeking feedback and making adjustments to meet individual/collective needs and learning styles. Huge kudos for navigating flexibility with grace and thoughtfulness. The instructors showed openness, vulnerability, and bravery throughout the course and created a space that allowed voices of experience and insight, as well as a place to listen, just listen. I wish this class existed as a pro-seminar with ongoing engagement and deeper dives into different facets of how to understand and dismantle systemic racism in health sciences. I will miss this community! Also, this class should be free."

"The focus on discussion in this class was a huge strength. Class time was all about exploring ideas and topics with fellow students, which led to bonding and deeper understanding of the material. Another strength was the focus on looking at racism through a systems lens – the instructors did a fabulous job of training us to think about the broader systems that we exist in, and how pieces of our lives fit in to different areas."

*"On the medical side, there is **no meaningful or impactful** support for students of color. When beginning my training, I found myself without a place to confide in trusted individuals to process the shock of attending a PWI in a majority-white city. It is clear to me that the few times we spoke about diversity in my training were not enough for any real learning, and was only a surface-level box to be checked. Here on the graduate side was the first time I was exposed to a course that was not just geared toward white students' learning, but students of color were given the opportunity to learn and grow as well. I am so grateful for the work Sarah and Antoinette have done to create this course and this space. I grew in taking this course. The deep self reflection, though painful, was life-changing. Within academia sure, but within my SOUL as well. I have let new kinds of love into my life because I was asked purposefully and firmly to contend with my fears and projections. This. Is. Extraordinary. And this is the type of healing/learning that will help me become a better student and leader. From the bottom of my heart, I am moved by you and your work, and I cannot wait to continue burning this flame in my life, and lighting every candle I meet. Thank you."*

"Diverse collection of materials to spark thinking, learning, and dialog. It was clear that much thought went into the design of materials AND the design of class flow (overall and daily structure). The course structure was honestly brilliant given how content built across the weeks and linked to other learning modules. Honestly, for a class with heavy and often controversial or triggering content, this class was super fun. I was able to think deeply about my own research. The systems lens worked well as an organizing principle and as a learning referent."

"Thank you so much for all the hard work you put into this course. It was so therapeutic in so many ways and it has truly been one of the highlights of my PhD at OHSU. This is the most connected I've felt to my program/peers/OHSU community and it is so important to feel that when 80% of my PhD has been in the pandemic. Thank you thank you thank you!"

6.5.3 Course Improvement Recommendations

- Gaining more personal perspectives from different marginalized communities through invited guest speakers
- Adding content about mutual aid and community care, linking systems of oppression back to the current scientific enterprise & more time to discuss additional topics
- Designated office/tutoring hour to emotionally debrief from difficult course content
- Adding additional deep reflective questions to homework and group discussion

6.5.4 Final project: Applying learnings into action

One of the REI Center's goals for YR-2 is to zero in on the graduate student admissions process, which includes reimagining with faculty and students, the criteria we use to grant admission to graduate training programs (see section 9.2). The final project for this course asked students to apply what they learned to transform the graduate admissions process. We informed students that we hoped to incorporate some of their ideas into our YR-2 efforts, that we will publish any

newly developed admissions process in an open-source platform, and that we will invite students to co-author any submissions if their ideas are incorporated. Racial equity education is only as useful as the application of those lessons to our everyday lives, policies, and procedures. This project is an example of how the REI Center co-creates solutions with our community, empowers our community to become active change agents, and provides credit for racial equity work. Student reflections on the final project are below:

"I loved the premise behind this final project. It tied together what we learned in the class (our group talked quite a bit about the systems view of oppression) but took it to the next level, trying to envision how change could happen in something very practical and applicable, grad school admissions. I think that it was also very useful for us to see just how difficult it is to come up with a reasonable solution that can easily be implemented. Talking about problems with graduate school admissions is easy - we can all see that there are a lot of issues and the system is not fair and does not do a good job taking into account different levels of opportunity between candidates. Coming up with a solution is hard, but it was fun to see how different groups approached the problem and, in my opinion, particularly interesting to see how different all of the solutions were between groups. I learned a lot from this group project and thought it was great."

"Initially I was very nervous about the idea because I felt that I wasn't smart enough to come up with any truly transformative ideas. It was very relieving to hear that it would be a group project and I absolutely cherish the time spent as a group. We had a wonderful time coming up with ideas and having long conversations about the consequences of those ideas. I honestly could not think of a better way to put into practice the concepts and strategies learned over the course of this class. The added knowledge that portions of our project could actually be used by an admissions committee gave it an air of importance that not only produced a greater enthusiasm towards the project but also led me to consider each portion of the project much more carefully and in depth."

"I loved that the final project focused on applying what we have learned to something REAL. After participating as the student representative on the admissions committee last year, I had A LOT of thoughts but did not feel like I had any power (or the right information) as an individual to convince faculty to reconsider aspects of the application. I'm SO happy that I was able to participate in this in a setting where it's more likely for voices to be heard and change to happen. Thank you!!"

"I think doing this project with the thought in mind that it may actually change a policy/process both increased the pressure and the excitement. Normally, a final project is working for something arbitrary, like a grade, where this felt like doing meaningful work that actually mattered, similar to how I feel when I am performing research experiments."

"I loved this as the final project. Even though the lack of diversity seen at OHSU stems from many reasons, I liked that we focused on just one. Hearing from other groups about the different ways they would change this one aspect gives a focused approach that makes it seem like we can actually all come together to help reform the policy. Thank you for taking our ideas and creativity seriously and be willing to share them with those who run admissions. Hopefully something will change due to all these minds coming together to tackle the problem!"

6.5.5 REI Center efforts supporting OHSU anti-racism goals- Student Feedback

Evaluation Question: OHSU is assessing whether the REI Center model might be useful in identifying and addressing embedded systemic racism within our institutions and departments. This class represents one of the approaches the REI Center is using to address systemic racism, by focusing on what we consider to be critical education, community building, and empowering our community members to become active change agents. With this understanding, how useful do you think this class was to achieve part of our goal?

"This class might be the most important course offered at OHSU. I think that REI centers that can tailor classes like this one to their own departments would be extremely beneficial. This course needed to be broad because it was open to the entire graduate campus, but would be even better if each REI center could run a focused class that directly caters to each department's unique system."

"SO USEFUL!! This class was probably the most useful class I have taken throughout graduate school. It was informative but also created a safe space for us to learn about the experiences that our peers have been through. We learned about the problems but then also focused on solutions to these problems. I thought this class was fantastic and a big step forward in addressing systemic racism. I feel much more knowledgeable and empowered moving forward."

"This was extremely useful. As a WOC [Woman of Color], I often shy away from topics like these when it's in an institution setting as conversations become 1) redundant 2) caters to white people and their feelings 3) solves nothing. This class was an action based organization that has actually left me hopeful."

"I think this class was incredibly useful. It was totally different than any other racism/bias class I have participated in, with a hugely beneficial mix of getting to know my fellow trainees (across departments); helping me think about things in a wider, systems lens, which highlights how tricky racism in high education is; and equipping me with the ability to DO something about it. This class should be taught more, and be required for all members of OHSU research (including faculty)."

"I think it was extremely useful. Every week I would go back to my lab to share what I learned and I think it has really changed how we all see our roles in science and society. I was telling my PI that this should be required for everyone to take."

"This class - even modules of it - would be central to achieving the goal of identifying and addressing embedded systemic racism. I have presented the work and my appreciation for it to departmental leadership around the value of building connections, embracing models, and thinking of research implications (research questions, as well as the broader research enterprise) in regards to systemic racism in [their program]. This class offered an opportunity to learn and gain new language for what had been really messy thoughts, and I am ever grateful. It offers common language and framework/mindset to work via a classroom community."

Evaluation Question: If your department/program has an REI Center, how useful do you think an REI Center is in advancing racial equity work in your own department/program? If your department/program doesn't have an REI Center, how useful do you think an REI Center would be to advance racial equity work in your own department/program?

Figure 4: Usefulness of the REI center

A) NGP students found the presence of an REI center within their department extremely useful (8/9) or moderately useful (1/9) in advancing racial equity within the department. **B)** Non-NGP students thought the presence of an REI center within their department would be extremely useful (5/5) for addressing racial equity.

7. Student support

The REI Center provided both individual and group student support. We aim to build trusting relationships with students and to be recognized as a place of support. The majority of PEER students within the Neuroscience Graduate Program have worked closely with the REI Center staff. We were frequently asked to provide in-depth individual support for the following topics:

Transitioning to graduate school & navigating imposter syndrome	Helping connect PEER students to therapist of color in Portland	Conflict resolution and increased communication with mentors	Guidance on navigating the research environment as a PEER student
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Note: Connecting PEER students with a therapist of color is an essential service as 1) finding therapists of color in Portland is particularly challenging (due to racial disparities in the field and poor coverage by health benefits); 2) many students of color express that finding a therapist of color is the only way they would feel comfortable seeking therapy; and 3) the lack of easily accessible therapists of color oftentimes inhibits/stalls students seeking therapy services.

The REI Center also hosted two sessions focused on students brainstorming ways the REI Center could support students. This type of community feedback is essential for us to determine if we are meeting student needs. Neuroscience Graduate Program students requested:

- Group meetings with the REI Center each month to cover topics that PEER students may need additional support on. We responded to this request immediately and started monthly meetings in the Fall of 2021.
- Offering specific sessions for international students during student orientation. We support this idea; however, this specific request is outside of the REI Center's scope. Alternatively, we coordinated an introduction between international students and leaders of student groups that are involved with planning student orientation, including the [Graduate Student Organization](#) and [Graduate Researchers United](#).

Additionally, the REI Center has quarterly meetings with the [Alliance for Visible Diversity in Science](#) in order to practice transparency and accountability. The REI Center shares our activities each quarter and solicits feedback that we incorporate into our future planning and initiatives.

7.1 Student Support Feedback

"During my time resolving conflict with [my] PI, I felt supported in finding the best way to mediate the situation. I greatly appreciated the several check-ins to assess the progress of the situation including those that were last minute when I was under a lot of stress over the situation. I also felt that because Antoinette and Sarah had first hand experience with this type of conflict resolution, my concerns were received with empathy. The REI center has allowed me to feel more included in my program as a first generation student of color as sometimes the barriers or intimidation arising from being one of the handful of marginalized students in the NGP has made it challenging to advocate for myself. I like that there is a focus on accountability and diminishing harmful power dynamics that may exist between students and mentors. Accountability was the outcome of my conflict resolution as I was given the tools to build a mentorship agreement which resulted in receiving an apology from my mentor about some of the ways [they were] being unsupportive or reactive to miscommunications. Through PEER monthly meetings, I have been able to feel a sense of community and truly feel like the REI center is safe space where I can be open and honest without fear of judgment." (Student)

"When a traumatic experience occurred in my life, initially I wasn't sure where to reach out to. The REI center not only recommended me with a list of therapists, but also resources for selecting the correct therapist. They also offered to reach out to therapists on my behalf. Their support helped me find the best therapist suited to my trauma and helped me to advocate what I needed in therapy. I would not be where I am today without their guidance." (Student)

"I had the pleasure of interacting with both Drs. Foster and Kisiwaa through coursework (Racial Equity in Academia and Beyond), AVDS, the REI Center, and personal interactions. I was extremely grateful for all of these moments of community/connection, but most specifically for some interactions where resources for mental health care were provided to me. I did, however, wonder about mandatory reporting and felt the need to protect others by not sharing some issues I was privy to. This is no fault of REI, rather fault of other arms of OHSU (specifically the SOM) where I did not know who to turn to for help. If possible, educating the other arms of the institution on how to handle issues related to race and equity to EQUAL THE CALIBER of the REI center would be something I hope OHSU pursues." (Student)

"Meeting with Antoinette and Sarah has helped ease a lot of the worries that I've had coming into graduate school. I was able to find a therapist through their help, and knowing that they are available to help me navigate any difficult situations that may arise calms my anxious mind. I am so glad to have the REI center and its members on campus!" (Student)

"As a PEER student, the REI Center's PEER Mentoring sessions have helped immensely with approaching fellowship essays. PEER Mentoring sessions serve to address topics relevant to navigating all aspects of academia and graduate school as a PEER student. Antoinette, Sarah, and Letisha let the students pick a topic and I picked "Fellowship Writing" as many of us were in the process of applying for various competitive fellowships. Writing for fellowships has been proven to be an arduous task with the looming responsibility of walking the reader through the various reasons that affect a PEER student's career and personal trajectory. Discussing how to effectively convey these messages in writing was a highlight of the REI PEER Mentoring Session and greatly aided in writing all my fellowships for Fall 2021. Such conversations were not previously indicated, offered, or suggested as this topic typically does not fall within the range of PWI [Predominately White Institutions] and PW-graduate programs." (Student)

8. Training grant development and support

A frequent unmet need for many faculty members, programs, and students is finding university-supported assistance in developing, writing, or editing diversity/racial-equity focused training grants. Currently, OHSU does not provide faculty or programs dedicated support in grant development or writing from personnel deeply knowledgeable in issues of racial equity. A benefit of having an REI Center embedded into local units is that we are uniquely positioned to provide one-on-one and small group grant development support. Over the last year, we assisted on the submission of three grants:

Grant name	Funding body	Type of grant	Type of faculty assistance
Gilliam Fellowship for Advanced Study	Howard Hughes Medical Institute	Student training grant	Idea development, writing, editing
Blueprint Diversity Specialized Predoctoral to Postdoctoral Advancement in Neuroscience (D-SPAN) Award	NIH	Predocctoral Fellowship	Guidance in writing the “Description of Candidate’s Contribution to Program Goals” document required from the sponsoring institution (OHSU Neuroscience Graduate Program)
Brain Initiative	NIH	Research Grant	Guidance in writing the “Plan for Enhancing Diverse Perspectives” document

“The REI Center was exceptionally helpful with our recent HHMI Gilliam Fellowship. I would like to highlight several specific aspects of this.

1) As part of this application process, we needed to highlight “our departments efforts to advance diversity and inclusion in graduate education”. We were able to highlight many of the efforts that the REI center has guided and/or implemented over the past year: helping to revamp our admissions review process, including training for faculty on the admissions committee; the creating of the NGP/Vollum Racial Equity Statement, which has positively impacted the number of PEER applicants to NGP; providing education for students and faculty through newly developed courses and training.

2) We also had to develop a plan for using the Advisor Diversity and Inclusion Award money (\$3000/yr/3yrs) as part of the application. We had discussions with Antoinette and Letisha about how this money could best be used to support and retain current PEER students in graduate programs at OHSU. They helped develop a plan for a series of workshops focused on topics important to PEER students: financial literacy for PhD students; career development and resources for careers beyond academic bench science; mental health and wellbeing through a cultural/racial/intersectional lens.

The assistance in developing these plans, and the feedback they provided, were critical for the application.” (Faculty)

“During my first 9 months as an Assistant Professor, my interactions with the REI have been for me both educational and inspiring. For example, Letisha provided critical feedback on my “Plan for Enhancing Diverse Perspectives” statement - a new pilot requirement for NIH grants – which helped me reflect not only on how I might recruit PEER students, but retain them, by creating a welcoming, supportive and fertile research environment.” (Faculty)

9. Program policy and procedure

The REI Center works to address racism on all four levels: individual, interpersonal, institutional, and structural. In order to effectively move towards an anti-racist institution, organizations must work to systematically dismantle the racism embedded in institutional policies, procedures, and practices that are upheld by system “norms”. As with all other activities of the REI Center, the approach to innovative policy requires working with equity and inclusion as the foundation. Equity values and racial equity guiding principles (Section 12.1) underlay all of our policy recommendations and process improvements including (but not limited to): transparency, clear communication, accountability, collaboration and collective action, stating explicit goals, continual learning, and importantly centering the voices and experiences of the marginalized. Furthermore,

the REI Center strives to dismantle systemic racism by actively opposing normalized and **white dominant culture** reinforced through policies and practices. Given that the goal of an equitable academic environment free from systemic racism does not exist anywhere, Innovative Policy functions from a place of experimentation where iterative data/information gathering is prioritized, and community engagement is integral to the planning and implementation stages of this work.

Figure 5: Framework for design and implementation of innovative policy using a racial equity and inclusion lens. Creation, implementation, and evaluation of new policies and procedures takes an iterative approach. Racial equity and inclusion values and guiding principles (blue text) are practiced and embedded at all steps in this framework.

Goals and milestones were developed for each initiative and for transparency and accountability, this information was shared in multiple public forums (Section 10) as well as published online.

In YR-1, three initiatives were completed, using an equity lens to develop and implement new policies and procedures for recruitment and retention of Vollum Institute faculty, postdocs, staff, and students of the Neuroscience Graduate Program. An additional three objectives originally planned for YR-1 (cluster hire strategies for new faculty, allocation of resources for PEER faculty, and conflict resolution) were deprioritized due to staffing limitations. These will be discussed with the Vollum Community in strategic planning for YR-2. Below we outline each

initiative and the procedural steps involved, the major equity values and guiding principles involved, and the evaluation strategy and initiative outcomes.

9.1 Enhance recruitment of prospective PEER applicants

The REI Center aimed to understand and expand the scope of advertising to create a more diverse applicant pool for prospective faculty, postdocs, staff, and graduate students. The following steps were taken:

1. Evaluating the current scope of advertising and developing an advertising inventory (data collection)
2. Providing recommendations for new passive and active advertising strategies
3. Creating a new process for advertising to reach communities of PEER scientists (implementation)
4. Annual evaluation of advertising strategies

9.1.1 Rationale: Equity Values, Guiding Principles, and Opposing System Norms

Identifying racial equity gaps in areas of recruitment and advertising was considered an immediate need in the REI Center. Oftentimes, the default reasoning for not having a diverse and inclusive environment is that a racially diverse candidate pool does not exist. Our approach involves not only broadening our reach to PEER communities but also striving to incorporate procedures that promote active rather than passive recruitment. This meant whenever possible skewing our recruitment and outreach strategies towards active methods that allowed for actual interaction with candidates (e.g., informational sessions, personalized/individualized communications). In this way we are working against systemic norms of passive recruitment (i.e., just posting an ad), and moving away from transactional relationships where the ultimate goal is “efficiency”, which often results in less authentic connections. Active recruitment strategies focus on transformational relationships where shared understanding and commitment are foundational. Building in the appropriate resources (human, financial, etc.) allows for the development of genuine connection that begins to build a culture of community and trust.

9.1.2 Evaluation Strategy and Outcomes

Our process began with gathering information on common advertising outlets for the Vollum Institute. The prospective student pool for the Neuroscience Graduate Program was used as a target outreach audience with the expectation that there would be overlap in the outlets used to identify students, faculty, postdocs, and staff. At the time of initiating this objective, we determined that there were 11 main recruiting outlets with 7 aimed at reaching PEER applicants. An extensive recruitment inventory was developed and from that 6 additional outlets were selected for enhancing recruitment of prospective PEER applicants (see table below), representing an increase in outreach to PEER communities from 64% to 76%. When choosing additional recruitment outlets from the inventory, we aimed to balance passive and active recruitment strategies and create a sustainable financial plan for these recruitment activities.

Pre-existing Recruitment Outlets				
Recruitment Type	Outlet	Program Cost (if any)	Specific for PEER Recruitment	Passive or Active Recruitment
Campus Visit	University of Puerto Rico	N/A	Y	Active
Conferences	Society for Neuro (SFN)/BP Endure	Expo registration (minimal cost)	Y	Active
Conferences	Annual Biomedical Research Conference for Minority Students (ABRCMS)	Expo registration	Y	Active
Conferences	Society for the Advancement of Chicanos/Hispanics and Native Americans in Science (SACNAS)	Expo registration	Y	Active
Database	Institute for Broader Participation (IBP) Pathways to Science	Membership Fee (minimal cost)	Y	Passive
Faculty Network	Faculty as Past LOR writers NGP admissions mailing list	N/A	N	Passive
Faculty Network	Faculty for Undergraduate Neuroscience (FUN) mailing list	Membership Fee (minimal cost)	N	Passive
Federal	NIH Grad Fair via IRTA	N/A	N	Active
Federal	NIH MARC program directors mailing list	N/A	Y	Passive
Society	SFN mailing list (undergrad/student membership)	N/A	N	Passive
Society	BP Endure Student Participants mailing list	N/A	Y	Passive
New Selections from REI recruitment Inventory				
Recruitment Type	Outlet	Program Cost (if any)	Specific for PEER Recruitment	Passive or Active Recruit
Database	National Name Exchange	\$600	Y	Active
Campus Visit	Preview event (by invitation for equity programs like Meyerhoff Scholars, U-RISE, McNair, etc.)	\$\$\$ travel	Y	Active
Campus Visit PNW MSI (virtual)	Pacific University (Federally designated Minority Serving Institution)	N/A	Y	Active

Campus Visit PNW MSI (virtual)	Warner Pacific University (Federally designated Hispanic Serving Institution)	N/A	Y	Active
Fellowship	Vanderbilt - Fisk Postbaccalaureate Program	N/A	Y	Passive
Federal	NIH Research Training Initiative for Student Enhancement (U-RISE) Program	N/A	Y	Passive
Federal	Bridges to the Postdoctorate Program (masters to PhD)	N/A	Y	Passive
Social Media	Twitter handles (e.g., BlackIn, additional online PEER communities)	N/A	Y	Passive

Submitted applications include a field about how the candidate heard about the position. We anticipate that as we increase the proportion of active recruitment strategies, we will see a similar increase in PEER demographics in the applicant and offer pools. These data will be tracked and analyzed internally each year with a goal to publish the data in five-year increments.

9.2 NGP Admissions Process Improvement - Applicant Racial Equity Essay

Although there is a consensus within biomedical research about the need for a holistic admissions review, little empirical evidence exists as to the ideal way to implement such a process. In coordination with the REI Center, the Neuroscience Graduate Program is taking an experimental approach to a holistic admissions process by focusing on identifying and addressing racial equity gaps. This is a multi-year, multi-step process requiring engagement from all stakeholders. Part of creating an inclusive environment is to normalize the importance of anti-racism work to current and prospective community members. Therefore, a major milestone in this process was to create a way to determine if a prospective student is a good fit for the culture we aim to cultivate, which in this case refers to being values aligned. The steps taken to begin this work was as follows:

1. Identifying effective strategies for improving admissions process (data collection)
2. Creating an application prompt and essay guidelines
3. Creating essay evaluation materials
4. Developing and implementing short- and long-term training and collaboration plan for the admissions committee
5. Annual evaluation of admissions program outcomes

9.2.1 Rationale: Equity Values, Guiding Principles, and Opposing System Norms

Design and implementation of a process improvement plan for embedding equity into graduate admission requires intentionality at every step. In our view, the most essential values underlying this objective are collaboration and collective action. We used a few different modalities for

community engagement including quarterly meetings with the student-led advocacy group the Alliance for Visible Diversity in Science (AVDS), incorporation of a final group project related to transforming the graduate admission process in the Racial Equity and Beyond course (Section 6.5.4) and delivering open forum presentations on the topic. Moving forward as we developed the strategy for process improvement, we remained dedicated to centering marginalized voices and those that would be most impacted by forthcoming changes - in this case students. This guiding principle reflects, in part, the rationale behind incorporating a racial equity essay instead of a diversity statement into the graduate program application. This mechanism allows us to consider values alignment specifically on racial equity for the incoming student body which is important in promoting positive student-to-student interactions during graduate training and building an inclusive culture. In addition, many schools' default to a diversity essay as a way to **virtue signal** anti-racist values but ultimately divert the attention away from the subject of race. Addressing racism requires intentionally bringing racism to the forefront rather than referring to blanket terms such as diversity, equity, and inclusion. Below are a few example diversity essay prompts from various (anonymized) universities gathered from online searches that allude to racial equity but lack specificity.

"The University is committed to cultivating an atmosphere that promotes diversity, equity, and inclusion. In 250 characters or less, please discuss any tangible action(s) you have taken in the past to promote these principles, and how you envision continuing to do so in the future."

"What does Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion mean to you? How could you, as a graduate student, contribute to improving Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion in science and society? Please keep your response to 3,000 characters."

"The statement should describe how your background and experiences demonstrate your commitment and ability to engage with issues of diversity and inclusion, and should also discuss how those commitments might be reflected in your graduate school career and beyond. Your statement should be no longer than 500 words. (Optional component for supplementary funding)."

To specifically focus on racial equity and model our values of collaboration and collective action for prospective students, the Neuroscience Graduate Program's Racial Equity Essay prompt read as follows:

In your racial equity essay, we would like for you to share your perspective on what the NGP racial equity statement means to the training environment for our graduate students and faculty. What is your interpretation of what we aim to achieve in pursuing racial equity within the NGP? Also, please describe how you could contribute personally to the NGP racial equity goals.

Because transformative work involves risk taking and continual learning, we have created several opportunities to interact with stakeholders and the broader Vollum Institute community to receive their feedback on this process, so that they may develop a deeper understanding of the issues, and to work together towards solutions.

[9.2.2 Evaluation Strategy and Outcomes](#)

The primary endpoint in evaluating graduate admissions process improvement will ultimately be evident partly by an increase in PEER matriculation, and importantly by increasingly positive attitudes of students (especially PEER students) in their experiences with the graduate admissions process and their impressions of the program's culture. Reaching these outcomes will likely take iterative procedural changes and several years of data collection. Feedback received from faculty through working on this transformative process and from prospective students through personal conversation have thus far been positive and beneficial for continual improvement.

"What I personally experienced as an admissions committee member was that our tailored anti-bias training was excellent and that the new essay was also excellent. Introducing clear rubrics and transparency (and examples) to this part of admissions seems obvious to do in hindsight, but no one has done it before. Really effective and a lot more fair than past years." (Faculty)

"It was clear from at least two [NGP prospective graduate students] that I remember well that the NGP racial equity essay was the best they had seen from any school they were applying to and it was very impressive to them and stood out. They told me it made them think NGP was serious about issues concerning racial equity and we weren't just doing lip service. They also told me they would be excited to be part of the center's work as NGP students. A number of applicants commented on the fact that they found the prompt thoughtful and they appreciated the chance to work on writing the essay. Sarah, Antoinette, and Letisha have been doing a ton of work for the online recruitment events and I can see from scrolling through the faces, body language in the virtual meeting room during the REI Center that what is being said is really resonating with folks - both PEER and non-PEER scholars. Lots of head nodding and taking notes. Recruits are asking great questions that indicate that they really listened." (Kelly Monk; Faculty/ NGP Director)

With this YR-1 objective we are specifically focused on outcomes of the racial equity essay and are preparing to analyze the demographic breakdown of racial equity essay scores binned by interviews, offers, and acceptances. Per a new university policy ([No. 02-90-055](#)) on graduation admissions committee composition and function, we also included a Faculty Observer who was "responsible for supporting admissions committees by providing useful and reliable feedback regarding the selection process and adherence to the principles of diversity, equity and inclusion". A report from the Faculty Observer will be provided to the committee outlining strengths and weaknesses of the admissions process. In future years, the Faculty Observer report will form the basis for discussion in admissions working group meetings and on-going strategic planning. A full report describing how the racial equity essay was incorporated into the admissions process (e.g., admissions committee training process), evaluating outcomes from the 2021 admissions cycle, and recommendations for continual equity-based process improvements for upcoming cycles will be available on the REI Center website (soon to be launched) after the NGP makes offers and receives acceptances for the incoming class.

"The REI Center has been incredibly helpful as we work to improve our application and admissions process for the Neuroscience Graduate Program. First, they have helped us develop a more holistic review process that seeks to de-emphasize the components of the application that often work against PEER applicants. Second, they worked with Vollum and NGP leadership to formulate the Racial Equity Statement. This is an important way for us to convey our values to prospective students, and we asked them to reflect on this and discuss how they could contribute to these efforts as student at NGP. This was a new component of the application this year, and was very helpful in evaluating the applicants. Third, they provided training prior to the application review process to help the committee members learn how to reduce their bias. Having this as an annual training immediately prior to admissions is an important reminder for the faculty. Overall, these efforts by the REI Center have been a huge success and have led to an increase in both the number of PEER applicants and interviewees. We can envision how implementing what REI did for NGP across departments/programs will leverage broader efforts [that] support the university's mission of enhancing racial equity." (Admissions Committee Co-Chairs)

9.3 Monitoring and Addressing Salary Adjustments for Postdoctoral Scholars

According to the [OHSU policy 03-10-045 for postdoctoral appointments](#), all incoming postdocs are to be paid according to the NIH pay scale with increases to salary made at two points each year: 1) on the hiring anniversary date to adjust for the accrued additional year of experience while employed as an OHSU postdoc and 2) when the NIH makes its annual update to the pay scale. While paying postdocs per the NIH pay scale is meant to standardize and ensure pay equity, monitoring and making adjustments overtime is not centrally managed at OHSU and depends on the internal mechanisms of each local unit. Without a dedicated plan and clear and continual communication with postdocs and their mentors (faculty Principal Investigators), it is easy for salary concerns to go undetected. The HR administrative personnel in the Vollum Institute had already begun to audit and adjust postdoc salaries when required. However, the REI Center learned through multiple channels that there was much confusion about if/when postdoc salaries should change over time and who was responsible for initiating necessary changes. To address this issue, the REI Center worked with Vollum Institute leadership to create a structured and consistent communication process with postdocs and faculty. The steps involved:

1. Consulting with OHSU administrative officials, the Director of Postdoctoral Affairs, and working with Vollum Institute leadership on a process for pay remediation (if necessary)
2. Supporting Vollum Institute leadership in communications with postdocs and faculty
3. Establishing a mechanism for annual communication to postdocs and faculty, salary review and adjustments if required, and process maintenance

9.3.1 Rationale: Equity Values, Guiding Principles, and Opposing System Norms

Central to implementing this new process of monitoring and addressing postdoc salaries was providing clear communication to all stakeholders, honoring the experiences of those most impacted (in this case postdocs), and building a redistribution of power in this process. Matters of pay are sensitive topics for many. In this case in particular, while Postdoctoral Scholars are employees, they are also short-term trainees paid via “soft money” (i.e., grant-funded) who are under the supervision of their faculty mentors. And for some others, the postdoc may be an employee of OHSU on a working visa status. In these circumstances, the faculty mentor holds an inordinate amount of power, and this may prohibit some postdocs from raising concerns about their pay for fear of negative career implications. This power difference is compounded when postdocs are from a marginalized community and/or are not permanent residents, potentially making these conversations even more difficult. Without a centrally managed mechanism for handling postdoc pay at OHSU, PIs may intentionally or unintentionally neglect to provide annual raises. However, a simple change in procedure could help alleviate the stress of this conversation for postdocs, provide postdocs a clear resource to turn to if they have concerns about pay, and also provide support to PIs to ensure their postdocs are paid in compliance with policy.

To mitigate some of these challenges, it was necessary for leadership to communicate directly with Vollum Institute faculty and Postdoctoral Scholars in a way that was not only consistent with OHSU policy around this topic but also was clear and transparent about how this is handled

internally. Going forward, all Vollum Institute postdocs and faculty will receive a reminder communication from the HR administrator in the first quarter each year regarding the process of annual updates to postdoc salaries and what they should expect for the year. The HR administrator will act as an intermediary for the postdoc and their faculty mentor, fielding questions and making salary adjustments on schedule and/or to resolve any errors. This shifts the power dynamic for more of a balance between the mentor and the trainee.

9.3.2 Evaluation Strategy and Outcomes

The REI Center worked with administrative personnel to create a salary self-assessment tool which was provided to postdocs so that they could check their pay records and determine if there were any discrepancies that may need to be reconciled. We also provided postdocs with a list of frequently asked questions (Section 12.7) and are working to publish both of these resources online for easy reference.

This, coupled with direct communication from leadership of the Vollum Institute, was meant to facilitate detection by individual postdocs in the case of anyone slipping through the cracks of the annual pay audit that was already taking place. Twice per year, the REI Center (with Vollum Institute leadership) will check in with the HR administrator to evaluate the number of salary concerns raised and corrections needed. Since initiating this process, we have had one check in with the HR administrator and were told that just a few postdocs raised questions and these were resolved without intervention (i.e., salary correction).

10. Presentations

Presentation title (with link if available)	Date	Presenter	Audience	Brief description
Racial Equity and Inclusion Center: What is it?	03/08/21	Letisha Wyatt & Antoinette Foster	Research and Innovation Townhall (OHSU)	Anti-racism education, introduction to the REI Center; Part 1 of 2
Racial Equity and Inclusion Center: How it works	04/26/21	Letisha Wyatt & Antoinette Foster	Research and Innovation Townhall (OHSU)	Strategic overview of YR 1 goals; Part 2 of 2
Equity in Open Scholarship	07/22/21	Antoinette Foster	United Nations Open Science Conference (External)	Applying racial equity and global oppression lessons from the COVID-19 pandemic to climate change solutions
Neuroscience Graduate Program Retreat	09/12/21	Letisha Wyatt, Antoinette Foster, Marc Freeman, & Kelly Monk	Vollum Institute/Neuroscience Graduate Program (OHSU)	Official introduction of REI Center to local unit; strategic overview of YR 1
Anti-racist Training for the Biomedical Research Community	10/06/21	Antoinette Foster	Group on Research, Education, and Training (GREAT) Virtual Conference; Association of American Medical Colleges (External)	Discussing strategies to integrate anti-racism education into graduate school coursework
Informational Webinars on NGP Admissions	10/12/21; 11/3/21, and 11/18/21	Letisha Wyatt	Prospective students to the Vollum Institute Neuroscience Graduate Program (OHSU)	Provided an overview to the REI Center function within the Vollum Institute/NGP and discussed the required racial

				equity essay (new application component)
Racial Bias in Graduate Admissions Training	10/29/21 11/1/21	Letisha Wyatt, Antoinette Foster, and Sarah KISSIWAA	NGP Admissions Committee (15 faculty and 2 graduate students)	Developed and delivered training on racial bias in graduate admissions
Workshops on Evaluating Graduate Application Racial Equity Essays	11/15/21 11/18/21 11/19/21	Letisha Wyatt, Antoinette Foster, and Sarah KISSIWAA	NGP Admissions Committee (15 faculty and 2 graduate students)	Hosted workshops to practice reviewing racial equity essays

11. REI Center Contact Information

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12. Appendix

12.1 Glossary

Term and link to reference (if available)	REI Center definition or linked reference definition
Anti-racism principles and Racial Equity principles	“Anti-racism” and “Racial Equity” principles are similar. Principles and processes that stand opposed processes and procedures that support a system of racism.
Anti-white supremacy principles and white dominant culture	Principles and processes that stand opposed to white supremacy culture, procedures, and processes.
Brave space	An environment that allows for critical and oftentimes challenging conversations about systemic oppression while centering respect, inclusion, compassion, and harm reduction.
Bottom-up approach	In reference to a hierarchical power structure, a bottom-up approach describes strategies executed at the lowest level of power that affect the entire organization. Both bottom-up and top-down (refer below) are required and essential for both whole system and organizational change.
Emergent Strategy principles	A set of organizing principles for realizing social justice/movement work. Principles originally written by adrienne maree brown; principles summarized here .
Liberating Principles	A set of ten leadership principles that act to guide our behavior as we work towards liberation from oppressive systems and structures.
Local unit	A term used by the REI Center to describe the focused area within OHSU that a single REI Center is dedicated to.
PEER	Persons excluded because of their ethnicity and race
Racial Equity Principles	Refer to Anti-racism principles above.
Racial Equity Values	Racial equity values that the REI Center uses to guide our work include transparency, accountability, collective action, equity, inclusion, harm reduction, and power redistribution
Radical Participation	Radical participation is a philosophy that describes a system

	<p>where every individual has something meaningful to contribute and participates accordingly. That means that our learning depends heavily on individual participation and contributions during and after class. There are many ways to participate, and all forms of participation are valued. Ways to participate include but are not limited to verbally contributing to discussions during class, silent gDocing (see below), writing in the chat on Zoom, and posting/responding to blog questions on Sakai.</p>
<p>Systemic racism</p>	<p>A system rooted in a racist foundation that is composed of intersecting, overlapping, and codependent racist institutions, policies, practices, ideas, and behaviors that give an unjust amount of resources, rights, and power to white people while denying them to people of color.</p>
<p>Systems lens</p>	<p>Also known as systems thinking, a systems lens is a practice and strategy of applying a holistic understanding of systemic racism or systemic oppression to events, experiences, or data.</p>
<p>Systems of oppression</p>	<p>Discriminatory institutions, structures, norms, policies, and practices embedded into our society and used to oppress groups of people.</p>
<p>Top-down approach</p>	<p>In reference to a hierarchical power structure, a top-down approach describes strategies executed at the highest level of power that affect the entire organization. Both bottom-up (refer above) and top-down approaches are required and essential for both whole system and organizational change.</p>
<p>Transformative futures</p>	<p>A concept that refers to a marked and comprehensive social and systems change in ways aligned with anti-racism, anti-white supremacy, and liberating principles, with a core focus on the redistribution of power.</p>
<p>Virtue signal(ing)</p>	<p>Virtue signaling strategies serve to reform or reinforce an organization's image as progressive, egalitarian, and committed to social welfare, while drawing attention away from injustices that the organization is directly responsible for. Institutional discourse risks being perceived as inauthentic if practices and outcomes do not reflect newly proclaimed values.</p>

12.2 REI Center Racial Equity Core Competencies

Learn

Purpose: Individuals obtain an educational understanding of fundamental educational racial equity concepts. *Learn* is divided into two elements.

Elements: 1) Core Concepts- Individuals gain a foundational understanding of core knowledge and learn useful frameworks for understanding racial equity. 2) Individuals expand on their core knowledge by understanding how racial equity relates to their institute/program/department and learn to apply a racial equity lens to their anti-racism work.

Core Competency I: Learn

Element	Competency Component
Core knowledge	Core knowledge I: Systems thinking; social construction of race; relationship between race and history, power, and capitalism; colonialism and decolonization (which also covers gender as a colonial construct); white normativity, exceptionalism
	Core knowledge II: Intersecting systems of oppression and intersectionality <i>specifically viewed through a systems lens</i> ; white supremacy and white supremacy culture; values and values-guided decision making
	Core knowledge III: Systemic oppression in our environment, our power, emergent strategy; racial equity principles, liberating principles; our responsibility and ability to create change; imagining transformative futures
	Understanding how race-based privilege and power contributed to racial inequities within society
	Understanding the concept of a “racial equity lens”
Expand	Understanding what a reduction in systemic racism looks like
	Understanding the specific areas of racial disparities within the institute/department/program
	Understanding and practicing the institute/department/program’s values
	Understanding the strategic plan of the Vollum-REI Center for achieving racial equity well enough to recapitulate the work alone as leaders.
	Knowing the scope of work for data collection and data-driven policies required for advancements in racial equity

Core Competency II: Grow

Purpose: Individuals identify, examine, and dismantle beliefs and attitudes that uphold systemic racism. *Grow* is divided into three elements.

Elements: 1) Beliefs- Individuals learn about common internal beliefs that contribute to systemic racism and use guided self-reflection to examine their own beliefs. 2) Attitudes- Individuals learn about the relationship between beliefs and attitudes and how these can manifest to uphold

systemic racism. Individuals will use guided self-reflection to examine their own attitudes. 3) Self-care- Racial equity work is mentally taxing. Individuals learn strategies and resources to care for themselves throughout this process.

Element	Competency Component
Beliefs	Understands commonly held beliefs that uphold systemic racism in society
	Understands commonly held beliefs that upholds systemic racism within the scientific enterprise
	Understands commonly held beliefs that upholds systemic racism within the institute/department/program
	Actively works to dismantle harmful internal beliefs through continually self-reflection
Attitudes	Develops skills to self-reflect on one's own beliefs that upholds systemic racism
	Understands the relationship between beliefs, attitudes, and systemic racism
	Develops skills to self-reflect on one's own attitudes that upholds systemic racism
	Actively works to dismantle harmful internal attitudes through continually self-reflection
Self-care	Understands anti-racism work involves a continual process of evaluating one's own values, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors as they relate to systemic racism and intersecting systems of oppression.
	Develops strategy/plan to ensure personal mental health and safety

Core Competency III: Act

Purpose: Individuals learn to apply *Learn* concepts to their institute/program/department. *Act* is divided into three elements.

Elements: 1) Evaluation- Individuals critically analyze and evaluate racial equity issues within their institute/program/department using a racial equity lens. 2) Solution finding- After identifying strengths and areas of improvement within their institute/program/department, leaders develop solutions using a racial equity lens. 3) Stakeholder communication- Individuals develop language and communication strategies to effectively communicate with stakeholders about ongoing racial equity work, current progress, and overall goals.

Element	Competency Component
Evaluation	Critically examining and analyzing racial equity issues within the institute/department/program
	Applying a systems and racial equity lens to racial issues within the institute/department/program to evaluate issues
	Disaggregating data by race in all analysis as a standard practice
	Developing the skills required to personally identify racial equity issues within the

	institute/department/program
Solution finding	Developing approaches to advance racial equity in one's own work (within the institute/department/program and within their own research)
	Applying racial equity analysis in institute/department/program practices
	Applying racial equity analysis in institute/department/program policy
	Facilitating discussions about racial equity within the institute/department/program/one's own lab
Stakeholder communication	Understanding and practicing nonviolent communication skills with stakeholder groups across the institute/department/program
	Developing effective language regarding racial equity
	Generate mechanism and plans for continual communication to the institute/department/program about racial equity work, current progress, and overall racial equity goals

REI Center

12.3 Racial Equity and Inclusion Center Code of Conduct

The vision of the Racial Equity and Inclusion Center (REI Center) is to empower individuals to create anti-racist environments within their workplace and beyond. We believe that inclusive environments are necessary for optimum health, wealth, and productivity; yet cultivating such an environment is oftentimes challenging. We are here to help!

We help members of our community identify and address systemic racism, white supremacy, colonialism, and other systems of oppression that are embedded within our scientific environment. In order to do this, we empower our members through anti-racist and racial equity education while working with our community to change harmful structures and policies.

In the interest of cultivating an environment where all members of the community see themselves as agents of change, we ask all individuals participating in REI Center activities to abide by the following code of conduct. This code of conduct is rooted in our values, identifies who we are addressing, and outlines expected/unacceptable behavior and the consequences of violating the code of conduct. The REI Center code of conduct is used in addition to [OHSU's Code of Conduct](#). This code of conduct was written and evaluated by all members of leadership at the REI center and is based off of the community guidelines from [PREreview.org](#).

Core Values

Equity and Inclusion

As our name suggests, equity and inclusion are our focus. We use a racial equity lens to assess the current institutional culture, determine cultural values and processes incongruent with racial equity, and develop strategic pathways for transforming cultural norms and practices to create racially inclusive environments for students, staff, and faculty.

Transparency and Accountability

Transparency is the foundation on which trust grows and develops and allows for accountability. The REI Center aims to be transparent and communicate to our community about REI Center initiatives in order for the community to hold us accountable to them. Through this, we hope to build a relationship of reciprocal transparency, accountability, and trust with our community. We encourage members of our community to communicate with us about their needs and concerns in cultivating an anti-racist environment.

Harm Reduction

It is important to us that every individual can participate in a welcoming and respectful environment when communicating with each other and with the REI Center staff. Although our center discusses topics that are inherently challenging, communicating in a way that considers the wellbeing of others is paramount and expected.

Who does this code of conduct apply to?

This code of conduct applies to any individual participating in REI Center activities, initiatives, or communications.

Expected behavior

Be respectful

Treat others with respect and dignity. Be sensitive to other perspectives, values and beliefs. Take responsibility for your impact and mistakes. If someone says they have been harmed through your words or actions, listen carefully, apologize sincerely and correct the behavior going forward.

Be direct but professional

Conversations about racial equity and systemic racism are difficult. For some of us, it may be the first time speaking about these topics. As such, disagreements and varying viewpoints may occur. It is important that we create a space where people can speak truthfully and respectfully. We expect that all individuals consider the wellbeing of others and contribute constructively.

Be inclusive

Encourage all voices. Be aware of how much time is taken by dominant members of the group. Provide alternative ways to contribute or participate when possible.

Unacceptable behavior

Violence and Threats of Violence

Violence and threats of violence are not acceptable - online or offline. This includes incitement of violence toward any individual, including encouraging a person to commit self-harm. This also includes posting or threatening to post other people's personally identifying information ("doxing") online.

Personal Attacks

It is not okay to insult, demean or belittle others. Attacking someone for their opinions, beliefs and ideas is not acceptable. It is important to speak directly when we disagree and when we think we need to improve, but such discussions must be conducted respectfully and professionally, remaining focused on the issue at hand.

Derogatory Language & Imagery

Hurtful or harmful language and imagery related to background, family status, gender, gender identity or expression, marital status, sex, sexual orientation, native language, age, ability, race and/or ethnicity, caste, national origin, socioeconomic status, religion, geographic location, and any other attributes is not acceptable. This includes deliberately referring to someone by a gender that they do not identify with, and/or questioning the legitimacy of an individual's gender identity. If you're unsure if a word or image is derogatory, don't use it. This also includes repeated subtle and/or indirect discrimination; when asked to stop, stop the behavior in question.

Unwelcome Sexual Attention or Physical Contact

Unwelcome sexual attention or unwelcome physical contact is not acceptable. This includes sexualized comments, jokes or imagery in interactions, communications or presentation

materials, as well as inappropriate touching, groping, or sexual advances. This includes touching a person without permission, including sensitive areas such as their hair, pregnant stomach, mobility device (wheelchair, scooter, etc.) or tattoos. This also includes physically blocking or intimidating another person. Physical contact or simulated physical contact (such as emojis like “kiss”) without affirmative consent is not acceptable. This includes sharing or distribution of sexualized images or text.

Violation of the code of conduct

Instances of unacceptable behavior may be reported directly by contacting REI Center leadership. Those who violate the code of conduct will be dealt with in a manner that is deemed necessary and appropriate for the circumstances, which may include temporary or permanent removal from REI Center activities or initiatives.

REI Center

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12.3 Syllabus: NEUS 618: Navigating the complexities of graduate school

Premise and course goals

A successful graduate student career involves more than experiments, publications, and presentations; it involves learning to navigate the complex sociopolitical structure and environment of academia. This course provides an essential and broader holistic approach to preparing students for graduate success by providing students with the context and tools to navigate the complexities of academic culture, mentor-mentee relationships, and mental health in graduate school.

This is not your usual course. It will use evidence based research as well as draw on the personal experiences of current and past graduate students to get at the crux of the mentee experience during graduate school (including those experiences not typically talked about). The course will meet for 3.5 hours per week for 5 weeks with a 1.5 hours wrap-up discussion.

This course will use a systems-thinking lens to provide the essential structure and support related to three main goals:

1. Provide an understanding of and tools to navigate the current scientific socio political system, beliefs, and attitudes embedded within academic culture that impact graduate students.
2. Address the complexities of the mentor-mentee relationship and provide useful tools to promote healthier relationships and better working environments.
3. Promote better mental health practices through graduate student training.

Contact information

Co-instructors and main points of contact:

Dr. Antoinette Foster- fostean@ohsu.edu

Dr. Sarah Kisiwaa- Kisiwaa@ohsu.edu

Official Course instructor

Dr. Letisha Wyatt- wyattl@ohsu.edu

Course meeting dates: 8/11, 8/18, 8/25, 9/1, 9/8, wrap-up at Kelly Monk's house on 9/10 at 5 PM.

Code of Conduct

The conductors and participants of this course are expected to abide by the Racial Equity and Inclusion Center (REI Center) Code of Conduct. This can be found here.

Learning approach

Our teaching philosophy adopts a constructivist approach to learning where students and instructors learn through sharing our experiences, identifying shared insights, self-reflection, receiving and giving feedback, and reflecting on it.

The different elements of the course are as follows:

- **Sakai-** All course materials and content will be housed in Sakai. If you are experiencing challenges navigating Sakai, please contact the Academic Support Counseling and Sakai Course Management System TLC Help Desk at 877-972-5249 or email TLC Help Desk (sakai@ohsu.edu).
- **Weekly course calls-** All weekly calls will be conducted through Zoom, except for our first meeting which is in-person (Room location TBD). To protect the privacy of all participants and to build trust within our group, our course calls will not be recorded. Learning from each other's experiences and insights are key to the mastery of the content, therefore recording the calls will be in violation of the REI Center Code of Conduct.
- **Grading-** Your grade for this course is on a binary Pass/Fail grading system. Course credit will be determined by the following factors:
 - **Attendance-** Weekly attendance is required and will be used to determine the final grade (Pass/Fail). We will take weekly attendance. If you cannot attend a class, please contact the co-instructors.
 - **Radical participation-** Radical participation is a philosophy that describes a system where every individual has something meaningful to contribute and participates accordingly. Our course is structured to reflect this philosophy. That means that our learning depends heavily on individual participation and contributions during and after class. There are many ways to participate and all forms of participation are valued. Ways to participate include but are not limited to verbally contributing to discussions during class, silent gDocing (see below), writing in the chat on Zoom, and posting/responding to blog questions on Sakai.
 - **Homework-** You will be given homework which you should complete by the requested date. Homework helps consolidate what you've learned during the class calls and provides a personal space for learning and reflection. Homework includes weekly assignments and short weekly surveys. Although homework will not be graded, the completion of the assignments will be used to determine your final grade. Homework should be submitted on Sakai.
 - **Self-assessment and surveys-** Reflecting is the best way to consolidate knowledge. We will be sending surveys to collect information about your experience in the course. This data helps us assess our effectiveness and identify ways to improve the class. The information you provide on the surveys will not be used to determine your grade. Similar to your homework assignments, the completion of the surveys will be used to determine your final grade.
- **Breakout rooms and shared insight-** During class calls, you may be assigned into breakout rooms to discuss a few questions with your fellow classmates. You will share your experience and listen to others'; at the end, everyone will re-enter the "main" room

and you will usually be asked to note down any points that you find insightful during the breakout room.

- **“Silent gDoc-ing” and +1s**-You will be asked to share your thoughts/experience using Google docs in response to class questions. You can also look at other folks’ responses and add +1s to the ones that particularly resonate with you. (This may not make sense now but we promise it will in the future!). The link to the gDoc is here.

💡 You won’t need a Google account to access these docs

Communication platforms

Zoom

Our cohort calls will be conducted using Zoom. You can access a Zoom room via its web interface, or the downloaded app. You can also use the phone to dial into Zoom (although you won’t see slides or faces, so it is recommended that you join our call using a computer with an internet connection). Course calls will not be recorded. Please make sure that you have working audio output (speakers/headphones) and a microphone which Zoom has the permission to access.

Sakai

Course communication is conducted primarily through OHSU email and through Sakai using their email, chat room, and blog post functions. We will store all relevant course information on Sakai.

Curriculum Overview

Week 1. Introductions and big decisions 8/11 1-4:30 PM PST (In person)

Learning objectives:

- Overview of the course, course expectations, introduction of course members, trigger warning (repeated every week)
- Factors to consider when choosing a mentor
- What does a “good” project actually mean? Evaluating safety and risk in thesis projects
- What the heck is a committee? Factors to consider when choosing your thesis committee

Week 2. Systems lens approach to conceptualizing academic culture 8/18 1-4:30 PM PST

Learning objectives:

- Exploring individual values
- What is culture and how is it created?
- Understanding academic culture-exploring values and beliefs in research
- Systems thinking and systemic inequities

Week 3. Expectations, boundaries, and contracts 8/25 1-4:30 PM PST

Learning objectives:

- Determining mentee and mentor expectations- what are they and why do you need them?
- Establishing mentor-mentee contracts & small group feedback
- The struggle of speaking up
- There is an issue! Where do I go to find support or solutions?

Week 4. Nonviolent communication 9/1 1:30-5:00 PM PST

Learning objectives:

- Violent vs nonviolent forms of communication
- Nonviolent communication model
- Identifying and understanding our feelings (no eye rolling!)
- Practicing nonviolent communication
- Setting healthy boundaries with your mentor

Week 5. Staying grounded during grad school 9/8 1-4:30 PM PST

Learning objectives:

- Exploring imposter syndrome
- Work-life balance- Is life work?
- Defining success and redefining failure
- Burnout and the dangers of staying ungrounded
- Mindfulness, breathing, & mental health resources

Week 5 assignment will be an end of the course survey that is distributed via email.

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12.4 Syllabus: NEUS 619: Effective Scientific Presentations

Premise

Scientists need to speak with confidence and impact to convey the significance of their findings. We need to do this with our peers as well as non-scientific audiences. Doing this effectively is challenging and requires deep reflection on what the main message is and the audience that it is being conveyed to. This course will focus on ways to help participants make effective slides and posters, develop verbal and non-verbal presentation skills and handle questions from the audience.

Goals

This course will help participants:

1. Assess their existing presentation skills and identify areas for improvement.
2. Clarify the objective of their presentation to help them and their audience stay on track.
3. Present scientific information so that the audience understands the significance of their findings.
4. Open presentations in a way that captures attention.
5. Design visuals that support the message
6. Design and deliver effective poster presentations
7. Manage Q&A

Contact information

Co-instructors and main points of contact:

Dr. Sarah Kisiwaa- kisiwaa@ohsu.edu

Courtney Bouchet- bouchet@ohsu.edu

Official Course instructor

Dr. Kelly Monk- monk@ohsu.edu

Course meeting dates: August 31st - September 10th 2021 9am-11am PST except September 1st which will be from 11am till 1pm.

Code of Conduct

The conductors and participants of this course are expected to abide by the Racial Equity and Inclusion Center (REI Center) Code of Conduct. This can be found [HERE](#).

Learning approach

Our teaching philosophy adopts a constructivist approach to learning where students and instructors learn through sharing our experiences, identifying shared insights, self-reflection, receiving and giving feedback, and reflecting on it.

The different elements of the course are as follows:

- **Sakai-** All course materials and content will be housed in Sakai. If you are experiencing challenges navigating Sakai, please contact the Academic Support Counseling and Sakai Course Management System TLC Help Desk at 877-972-5249 or email TLC Help Desk (sakai@ohsu.edu).
- **Course calls-** All calls will be conducted through Zoom.
- **Grading-** Your grade for this course is on a binary Pass/Fail grading system. Course credit will be determined by the following factors:
 - **Attendance-** Attendance is required and will be used to determine the final grade (Pass/Fail). We will take attendance. If you cannot attend a class, please contact the co-instructors.
 - **Radical participation-** Radical participation is a philosophy that describes a system where every individual has something meaningful to contribute and participates accordingly. Our course is structured to reflect this philosophy. That means that our learning depends heavily on individual participation and contributions during and after class. There are many ways to participate and all forms of participation are valued. Ways to participate include but are not limited to verbally contributing to discussions during class, silent gDocing (see below), writing in the chat on Zoom, and posting/responding to blog questions on Sakai.
 - **Homework-** You will be given homework which you should complete by the requested date. Homework helps consolidate what you've learned during the class calls and provides a personal space for learning and reflection. Homework will include creating a ten minute oral presentation to be presented to the class on the last day. Although homework will not be graded, the completion of the assignments will be used to determine your final grade.
- **Breakout rooms and shared insight-** During class calls, you may be assigned into breakout rooms to discuss a few questions with your fellow classmates. You will share your experience and listen to others'; at the end, everyone will re-enter the "main" room and you will usually be asked to note down any points that you find insightful during the breakout room.
- **"Silent gDoc-ing" and +1s-** You will be asked to share your thoughts/experience using Google docs in response to class questions. You can also look at other folks' responses and add +1s to the ones that particularly resonate with you. (This may not make sense now but we promise it will in the future!)

💡 You won't need a Google account to access these docs

Communication platforms

Zoom

Our cohort calls will be conducted using Zoom. You can access a Zoom room via its web interface, or the downloaded app. You can also use the phone to dial into a Zoom (although you won't see slides or faces, so it is recommended that you join our call using a computer with an internet connection). Please make sure that you have working audio output (speakers/headphones) and a microphone which Zoom has the permission to access.

Sakai

Course communication is conducted primarily through OHSU email and through Sakai using their email, chat room, and blog post functions. We will store all relevant course information on Sakai.

Curriculum Overview

Day 1: Why we need but also hate presentations (Tuesday August 31st 9-11am PST)

- Overview of the course, course expectations, introduction of course members
- Fears and concerns about presentations
- Learning to enjoy presentations
- Planning your presentation
 - What is your story? (Introduction, body, conclusion)
 - What is it you want the audience to walk away with?
 - What information do you need for the audience to understand the story?
 - What is the best way to present this information?

Day 2: Planning your presentation continued (Wednesday September 1st, 11am - 1pm PST)

- Planning your presentation
 - What is your story? (Introduction, body, conclusion)
 - What is it you want the audience to walk away with?
 - What information do you need for the audience to understand the story?
 - What is the best way to present this information?

Homework

Pick a topic that you have researched on and answer the planning questions:

- What is my story? (Introduction, body, conclusion)
- What is it that I want the audience to walk away with?
- What information do I need for the audience to understand the story?

This is with the intention of creating a 10 minute presentation for the class (So think about how much information you need to get your point across). Submit the planning document to Sakai.

Day 3: PowerPoint basics (Thursday September 2nd, 9am - 11am PST)

- Font style/size
- Color contrast
- Layout (heading, text, lists)
- Use of empty space

- Use of images, animations
- Busy slides
- Alignment

Day 4: Structuring your talk (Friday September 3rd, 9am - 11am PST)

- Creating an engaging introduction (the need for a solution, need for new knowledge)
- Preparing good transition between slides (for logical storytelling)
- Signaling language (To alert the audience of new topic or conclusion)
- Writing effective summaries and concluding your talk

Day 5: Practicing, Feedback, Managing Q&A and nerves (Tuesday September 7th, 9am - 11am PST)

- Practicing
 - Why is it important?
 - Different ways of practicing
 - Things to look for while practicing
- Feedback
 - Frustrations surrounding feedback
 - Importance of feedback
 - When to get feedback
 - Accepting and incorporating feedback into your presentation
- Managing Q&A
- Managing nerves

Homework

Write a script and practice your talk then either:

- Video or voice record yourself and critique yourself. Submit your critique of yourself to Sakai,
- Practice your talk to someone and obtain feedback. Submit the feedback to Sakai.

Day 6: Poster Presentations (Wednesday 8th September, 9am - 11am PST)

- Planning
- Structuring
- Designing
- Presenting

Day 7: Individual Presentations (Thursday 9th September, 9am - 11am PST)

Day 8: Individual Presentations (Friday 10th September, 9am - 11am PST)

Homework:

Submit your feedback to presenters on Sakai.

REI Center

12.5 Syllabus: NEUS 644 Racial Equity in Scientific Research and Beyond

Premise and course goals

This course provides foundational knowledge and skills required to address racial inequities, with a particular emphasis on inequities that exist in academia. Students will develop a systems perspective on the historical basis, structure, and impact of systemic racism outside and within the scientific enterprise. Students will tackle three common barriers to equity: learning, discussing, and addressing racial inequities. This course is meant to empower students by developing the knowledge and skill set to become active agents of change within their own environments, both within and outside of their program or institution.

This course will use a systems-thinking lens to provide the essential structure and support related to four main goals:

1. Obtain an educational understanding of racial equity topics including systems thinking, the social construction of race, race, history and power, white supremacy, and colonialism.
2. Learn how the topics in point 1 are embedded into the structure and landscape of the scientific enterprise.
3. Learn to identify, examine, and dismantle individual beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors that uphold systemic racism and racial inequities via group discussions and guided self-reflection.
4. Practice applying learnings to identify areas of racial equity improvement within their own lab/program/department. As a class, students will work together to develop and implement solutions using a racial equity lens.

Contact information

Co-instructors and main points of contact:

Dr. Antoinette Foster- fostean@ohsu.edu; Dr. Sarah Kisiwaa- kisiwaa@ohsu.edu

Course director:

Dr. Letisha Wyatt- wyattl@ohsu.edu

Course meeting dates: 09/27/21-12/17/21 9am-10:30am PST

Code of Conduct

The conductors and participants of this course are expected to abide by the Racial Equity and Inclusion Center (REI Center) Code of Conduct. This can be found here.

Learning approach

Our teaching philosophy adopts a constructivist approach where students and instructors learn through sharing our experiences, identifying shared insights, self-reflection, receiving and giving feedback, and reflecting on it. The different elements of the course are as follows:

- **Sakai-** All course materials and content will be housed in Sakai. If you are experiencing challenges navigating Sakai, please contact the Academic Support Counseling and Sakai Course Management System TLC Help Desk at 877-972-5249 or email TLC Help Desk (sakai@ohsu.edu).
- **Weekly course calls-** All weekly calls will be conducted through Zoom. To protect the privacy of all participants and to build trust within our group, our course calls will not be recorded. Learning from each other's experiences and insights are key to the mastery of the content, therefore recording the calls will be in violation of the REI Center Code of Conduct.
- **Grading-** Your grade will be determined by the following factors:
 - **Attendance-** Weekly attendance is required and will be used to determine the final grade. We will take weekly attendance. If you cannot attend a class, please contact the co-instructors. (5% of grade). Three excused absences are permitted before impacting the final grade.
 - **Radical participation-** Radical participation is a philosophy that describes a system where every individual has something meaningful to contribute and participates accordingly. Our course is structured to reflect this philosophy. That means that our learning depends heavily on individual participation and contributions during and after class. There are many ways to participate, and all forms of participation are valued. Ways to participate include but are not limited to verbally contributing to discussions during class, silent gDocing (see below), and writing in the chat on Zoom. (30% of grade)
 - **Class assignments-** You will be given class assignments that you should complete by the requested date. Class assignments help consolidate what you've learned during the class calls and provide a personal space for learning and reflection. Class assignments include weekly reading podcasts, weekly written responses, presentations, and a final project. (Weekly reading/written assignments are 30% of grade; Final project is 30% of grade).
 - **Final project-** While one part of racial equity is learning, the other part is putting learnings into actions. The final project in this course will be a group project that helps apply the concepts learned throughout this course into real tangible actions. For the final project, students will choose to work on one of two racial equity efforts that focus on their policy change or education/community building at OHSU. Each racial equity effort is meant to help students build the capacity, skills, and confidence to impact and drive change within their local university environment. The specific topics will be determined as a class.
 - **Self-assessment and surveys-** Reflecting is the best way to consolidate knowledge. We will be sending short surveys to collect information about your experience in the course. This data helps us assess our effectiveness and

identify ways to improve the class. The information you provide on the surveys will not be used to determine your grade. Like your class assignments, the completion of the surveys will be used to determine your final grade. (5% of grade)

- **Breakout rooms and shared insight-** During class calls, you may be assigned into breakout rooms to discuss a few questions with your fellow classmates. You will share your experience and listen to others'; at the end, everyone will re-enter the "main" room and you will usually be asked to note down any points that you find insightful during the breakout room.
- **"Silent gDoc-ing" and +1s-** You will be asked to share your thoughts/experience using Google docs in response to class questions. You can also look at other folks' responses and add +1s to the ones that particularly resonate with you. (This may not make sense now, but we promise it will in the future!). The gdoc can be found here.

💡 You won't need a Google account to access these docs

Communication platforms

Zoom

Our cohort calls will be conducted using Zoom. You can access a Zoom room via its web interface, or the downloaded app. You can also use the phone to dial into Zoom (although you won't see faces, so it is recommended that you join our call using a computer with an internet connection). Course calls will not be recorded. Please make sure that you have working audio output (speakers/headphones) and a microphone which Zoom has the permission to access.

Sakai

Course communication is conducted primarily through OHSU email and through Sakai using their email, chat room, and blog post functions. We will store all relevant course information on Sakai.

Curriculum Overview

September

Monday 27th

- Class introduction

Wednesday 29th

- Class discussion: **Discovering your racial socialization**

October

Monday 4th

- Class discussion: **Human systems, systemic racism and intersectionality**

Wednesday 6th **Class canceled**

Monday 11th

- Class: discussion **Socialization and racial myths**

Wednesday 13th

- Class: discussion **Almost All Aliens**

Monday 18th

- Class: discussion **the origin and social construction of race pt. 1**

Wednesday 20th

- Class: discussion **the origin and social construction of race pt. 2**

Monday 25th

- Class discussion: **The origin and social construction of race pt. 3**

Wednesday 27th

- Class discussion: **The role in science in the initial construction of race**

November

Monday 1

- Class: discussion: **Colonialism as a system of oppression**

Wednesday 3rd

- Class: discussion: **Gender and colonialism**

Monday 8th

- Class: **Decolonization- what does it mean?**

Wednesday 10th

- Class: discussion Decolonizing science & introduction to the final project

Monday 15th

- Class: discussion: Personal values and the revolution of values

Wednesday 17th

- Class: discussion: **Characteristics of white supremacy culture & white supremacy culture in academia**

Monday 22nd

- Class discussion: **Emergent strategy introduction**

Wednesday 24th

- Class discussion: **Emergent strategy and racial equity principles**

Monday 29th

- Class discussions: **Exploring our personal role in anti-racism and liberation**

Wednesday 1st

- **In-class working session for final project**

December

6th/7th

- **In-class working session for final project**

13th/15th

- **Class presentations and Closing group discussion**

REI Center

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12.6 REI Center Racial Equity Essay Scoring Documents

Prompt: In your racial equity essay, we would like for you to share your perspective on what the NGP racial equity statement means to the training environment for our graduate students and faculty. What is your interpretation of what we aim to achieve in pursuing racial equity within the NGP? Also, please describe how you could contribute personally to the NGP racial equity goals.

Understanding the Challenges & Getting Involved w/ Racial Equity in STEM	
Score = Unsatisfactory	Unaware or disbelief of systemic challenges & the system of racism (no signs they went to our links)
	Unaware or disbelief of personal racism (individual values, beliefs, thoughts, & prejudices that harm members of PEER communities)
	Largely avoids the topic of racism (may bring up race but avoids talking about racism)
	Little expressed knowledge of the topic (no signs they went to our links)
	Lack of interest/Personal responsibility
Score = Satisfactory	Essay shows aspects of unsatisfactory scores as well as excellent scores
Score = Excellent	Expressed knowledge of individual/systemic challenges and why the work is important
	Discusses the topic and shows depth of understanding (e.g., concepts like equity/inclusion/systems)
	Demonstrates interest in the topic or willingness to learn
	Describes current involvement and/or clear ideas on potential to act

The following material on “Red flags” was adapted from:

<https://www.timeshighereducation.com/campus/diversity-statements-what-avoid-and-what-include>

Red flags: Common mistakes or pitfalls when writing the racial equity statement may fall into three major categories:

- Diversity by proxy
- Personal stories disconnected from larger systemic issues
- Avoidance with the topic/talking about race

1. Diversity by proxy

Diversity by proxy is when applicants borrow from the success of others around them, an organization or program. The applicant may speak specifically about their department’s demographics or a program for people of color that they have **minimally** interacted with.

Example 1: “_____ (university’s name) is one of the most diverse campuses in the country. We are _____% white, _____% Latin, _____% Asian/Pacific Islander, _____% African American.”

Example 2: Applicants might mention success and claim some responsibility for other people of color due to their passive engagement. “During senior year in undergrad I tutored at the Student Services Center and we have had many wonderful, bright students of color who just need intense mentorship. Due to the mentorship that they received in the Center, now these students are successfully in graduate programs”

Example 3: The message of “I support success for people of color” can be followed by surprise and/or self-congratulation. “I went to a high school with many disadvantaged students and a couple of them have gone on to grad programs at very good schools!”; or “I had one Black professor in college who was impressively articulate and actually turned out to be the best math teacher I’ve ever had!”

We call this “diversity by proxy” because the applicant’s example relies on numbers that tell us about where they are and not who they are or what they have done. Secondly, they are borrowing identity, status and achievement by linking themselves to the success stories of students or faculty of color. In this way, they give undue credit to themselves as a savior.

2. Personal stories disconnected from larger systemic issues

Applicants write of personal experiences that have occurred in their personal life that are meant to reflect their appreciation for diversity and inclusion and their dissatisfaction with racism without discussing the larger systemic issues.

Example 1: They may write about an event that solidified their understanding of privilege: “I grew up in a small town where there was only one Indian family and one of the girls from that family became a close friend. And then, in the sixth grade, everything changed. She and I both auditioned for the school play, *Annie*, and it was clear that another girl got the lead because she was white and looked the part. But my friend was clearly better than everyone else. I felt bad for her but there was nothing I could do. And that is why I really feel so strongly about racism and exclusion and do what I can to help students of color.”

Example 2: They may also talk about how they work with and learn so much from students of color. The focus is only on their feelings and how they assuage their feelings of social injustice by their engagement with people of color rather than consideration or engagement with broader systemic issues.

3. Avoidance of the topic/talking about racism specifically

Applicants write that they are in favor of diversity and inclusion but show no current or future initiative for engaging in racial equity issues, OR largely avoids discussing race in general.

Example 1: “Diversity is important in science but I haven’t had much time to think about these issues yet.”

Example 2: “Diversity is important but I haven't had much exposure” and then fails to provide any evidence of having informed themselves or avoid discussing any future initiative to inform themselves.

Example 3: “I believe in diversity, but there's not much I can do as a student because I have not been in a position where I might make decisions. I would be supportive if there were some people of color.”

Example 4: “I think diversity is important. I myself am a woman who is marginalized in science.” (or applicants discuss the issues/needs of other marginalized groups without saying anything about racism and systemic racism).

Example 5: “Diversity is good but people should get in based on merit”.

These red flags suggest that impact can only be made from certain positions, thereby exonerating most people who do not go against the grain. This obscures the roles that everyone plays in maintaining the status quo and contributing in small and large ways to discriminatory practices and negative outcomes for faculty, staff and students of color.

REI Center

12.7 REI Center FAQs for Postdoc Pay

- How do I determine my salary at hiring and any adjustments I've received?
 - All OHSU employees and students may view their salary information anytime! Follow the instructions below to do so:
 - Log on Oracle at ais.ohsu.edu by entering your OHSU username and password (note: you must be securely connected to the OHSU network by either accessing Oracle on campus or using the remote (Citrix/VPN) options if off campus).
 - In the "Navigator" menu, select "Employee Self Service OHSU AIS"
 - Select the "My Information" button from the list
 - Select the "Salary" tab
 - For each row, note the "Change Date" and the "Annualized Salary" columns for comparing to the NIH salary pay scales
- Does the source of funding matter when determining my pay?
 - No, all postdocs at OHSU are to be paid per the NIH pay scale and according to their level of postdoctoral experience. You will find the following text about this at the bottom of the OHSU Office of Postdoctoral Affairs webpage about salaries: "For Postdoctoral Scholars paid by stipend, specifically those on training grants or individual fellowships, the salary scale is set by the external funding agency. If the external funding agency's salary scale is lower than the OHSU FY2021 minimum guidelines for years of experience, the principal investigator or department must supplement the postdoc's salary up to the minimum".
- Is it up to my PI to determine my pay and/or make salary adjustments?
 - No, your pay is set by OHSU policy 03-10-045, postdoctoral appointments. Item 7 in that policy states that OHSU pays in accordance with the NIH scale and at the appropriate level of experience.
 - The Vollum Institute HR administrator is providing internal oversight on postdoc salaries and making postdoc salary adjustments when needed on behalf of the PIs. You do not need to contact your PI for salary adjustments. Reach out to the HR administrator directly to discuss any questions or concerns that you may have.